

Representation of Male and Female Self: A Disabilities Studies Inquiry

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Abstract:

The present paper analyses the play Tara by an acclaimed modern Indian playwright Mahesh Dattani, from Disabilities Studies perspective. The play has been analysed through various perspectives earlier. E.g. application of feminism, modernism, and postmodernism etc. but very few studies applied Disability Studies perspective. The present article discusses about various theories of Disability Studies. It is mainly concerned with the ways in which disabled people are treated, especially in the context of India. The present study applies an interdisciplinary approach to analyse the play. It combines anthropology, sociology, gender studies etc. The study has found that disabled persons are always treated with either pity or disgust. Especially disabled women because they are subject to double oppression in the society. The play clearly shows this through the two characters, Tara, and Chandan, who were born as conjoined twins. The present article shows how Dattani uses the family of disabled children as a microcosm to show the struggle of the typical Indian family which has disabled members.

Keywords: Disability Studies, ancient/religious model, medical/medieval model, modern/social model,

Introduction:

Born in Bangalore, Mahesh Dattani is one of the prolific dramatists of Modern Indian Theatre. Most of his plays deal with social issues of India, especially issues related to women. His first complete play is, *Where There's a Will* (1988.). In this play, Dattani talks about gender roles as prescribed by typical Indian patriarchal family. Dattani can be considered as the dramatist who clearly discusses about oppression of women in India. His other famous plays are, *Dance Like a Man*, *Bravely Fought the Queen*, *Seven Steps Around the Fire*, *Final Solutions*.

His play, *Tara* sheds light on the plight of disabled women in India. In this play, Dattani clearly portrays how disabled women are triply oppressed by Indian society through the main character of the play Tara.

An Overview of Disability Studies:

The appearance of the field Disability Studies has its roots in American Disabled People Rights Act 1990. This act clearly prohibits the discrimination of disabled people in all spheres of life. Influenced by this act, scholars like Rosemary Garland Thomson, Tom Shakespeare, Lennard J. Davies wrote extensively on Disability Studies. This resulted in appearance of Disability Studies in western academia.

Consequently, Disability Studies also emerged in India, a land in which physical impairment has a long history starting from Vedas, Epics etc. scholars like Anita Ghai, Ved Mehta, Firdaus Kanga wrote on issues of disabled people in India.

Theories of Disability:

Scholars of Disability Studies mainly advocated four theories of disability. They are,

1. Ancient/Religious Theory/Model. This is an old and prevalent theory of disability, especially in India. Because many superstitions are associated with a disabled child. The typical Indian Family always believes that the birth of a disabled child is like a curse. It is a retribution for their or the child's misdeeds in the previous life. This attitude can be seen the play in *Tara*, where Bharati, mother of the conjoined twins always faces various

psychic problems. Even at the end of the play, Bharati is being admitted to a psychiatric institution.

2. **Medical Theory/Model.** This theory advocates that disability is a medical issue, which must be treated through medical intervention. Many disabled activists, scholars oppose this notion. They argue that disability is not a defect which needs medical intervention. Rather, disability is just a form of diversity of a human being. Further they state that disability is just a unique existence of human being just like LGBTQ people. This theory is slight problematic. According to famous Disability Studies scholar of America, Tom Shakespeare, it is difficult to restrict disability to any single theory. Rather disability should be dealt with psycho-medical-social aspect.

Throughout the play *Tara*, it is evident that how a typical Indian family copes with disability through medical aid. The character, DR. Thakkar represents this and the play is full of events of visiting of the doctor to treat the twins. In the first scene, it is clear how disability is entirely considered as a medical issue;

Chandan: (jovially). “Doctors. Nurses. A painful necessity in our lives.” (Dattani, 333).

3. **Social Theory/Model.** This theory considers disability; disabled people are treated with pity, fear, or disgust. Most of the disability studies scholars endorse this theory. They argue that it is the attitude or treatment of the society which make disabled people as well as society to think that they are inferior to abled people, they lack something. Famous American disability studies scholar, Rosemary Garland-Thomson states that, “like gender, disability is also a socially and culturally constructed phenomenon.” (Rosemary, 6). This notion of society regarding disabled people is evident in the play. The characters, Roopa, Malini, and Prema were always showing disgust toward the twin disabled characters, Tara, and Chandan. In one of the acts of the play, we see a scene where the above mentioned three characters demonstrate their hatred with a poster, on which they wrote, “We Don’t Want Freaks.” This clearly shows how disabled people are subjected to oppression by the society.
4. **Personal Tragedy Theory/Model.** It is related to the struggle of individuals of disabled who cope, try to overcome disability. Due to excessive priority given to medical and social model, disabled people are compelled to think that they lack something, and they are burden to their family as well as to the society. This is evident throughout the play where the twin disabled characters always think about their lives.

Disability and Disability Studies in India.

Like other third world nations, India still has some belief in various superstitions. It is evident by the treatment of family towards its disabled member and the society's treatment of disabled people. Anita Ghai, one of the prominent activists has described about her own experience to show the superstition of Indian society. During one of the solar eclipses, the members of Ghai's family dug a hole in the ground and kept her inside that hole. Only her head was outside. Her entire body part was covered by the mud. This made her to suffer mentally. Ghai strongly argues that people with able bodies are also not completely independent. In one or the other way, every person, like disabled person, depends on another. And she also says that every individual has his/her own defects, no one is complete, normal.

Disability in the play *Tara*.

When the present study analysed the play *Tara* in detail, it confronted many contemporary Indian issues of society. The plight of women in Indian patriarchal family is a dominant one. But the play also sheds light on the issue of disability and the dire condition of a woman, who was born with impairment. In the play, there are two main characters, those are, Tara, and Chandan, who were born with a rare disease which affects one pregnant woman among fifty thousand women. After their birth, the twins undergo various diagnoses throughout their life. But their treatment by the family and the society is very different. The family provides more privilege to Chandan than Tara. But Bharati, the mother of the twin was concerned with the fate of her daughter. Her concern is clear in one of the scenes of the play;

Bharati. "Yes Chandan, The world will tolerate you. The world will accept you-but not her! Oh, the pain she is going to feel when she sees herself at eighteen or twenty. Thirty is unthinkable. And what about forty and fifty! Oh God" (Dattani, 349)

This shows about the mental torture of family. This applies to most of the Indian family who has a disabled member, especially if the member is a woman. The treatment of a disabled girl child by their parents is also very different from that of the disabled boy. Throughout the play, it can be seen Patel, father of the disabled twins, shows a lot of concern towards Chandan. Patel always insists Chandan to go for higher education, so that Chandan could

assist his father in his company. But when it comes to Tara, Patel portrays a typical most of the father towards a disabled girl child.

Dattani is very minute in his depiction of Indian family with disabled child. In society, most of the family is not at all ready to disclose the identity of their disabled girl child. One major reason for this attitude of the family is that, they fear about how they can be treated by the society. And the question of marriage is also one. The parents of disabled child think that, if they disclose the identity of their children, especially girl child, no one comes forward to marry them. This is also seen in the play, where Bharati rejects Patel's idea that one of the doctors had decided to publish the miracle survival of the conjoined twin, who were Tara and Chandan to show the growth of modern medical world.

In another instance, Bharati tries to bribe Roopa, a neighbour girl. Bharati requests Roopa to befriend with Tare. Because there is general belief that disabled person need someone for their aid for physically as well as mentally.

Bharati says to Roopa, "if you promise to be her best friend-I will be most grateful to you and I will show it ...in whatever you want me to." (Dattani, 341)

But it is also very difficult to argue that Bharati is genuinely concerned with her disabled daughter's future. Because it was she who decided to keep Chandan normal in cost of the life of her daughter Tara. When the family comes to know that they were getting a rare twin who share the single body for their survival and the twins have only three legs instead of four and DR. Thakkar informs them that the leg of the girl child is in normal conditional, only the boy baby has the defect, then they decide to keep alive the baby boy at the cost of baby girl. Of course, Patel rebukes this. But it was of no use. Because the father of Bharati was an MLA and he bribed DR. Thakkar to save the boy. Bharati also accepts this. So, some scholars argue that Bharati suffers regret for her act. And to hide the truth, she shows a lot of concern to Tara.

Treatment of Disabled People.

In the play, the characters, Roopa, Prema and Malini represent some people of the society's treatment of disabled people. These three characters are very eager to know more about Chandan and Tara. They treat Tara and Chandan as well as Bharati as belonging to

another race. After meeting Tara's family for the first time, Roopa immediately goes to Prema and Nalini to tell them about the family, she says,

Roopa. "Guess what? I went to her house! Yes. Right inside! I met everyone there. She is a real freak feature of nature all right, but wait till you see her mother! Oh God! I can't tell you-she is really...wandh tarah. Oh God! I will never go there again." (Dattani, 342)

This shows how some people of the society have prejudice toward the family, which has a disabled member. And even after declaring that she would not go again to Tara's family, Roopa again goes to Tara's family. This shows the hypocrisy of the society. Because on the one hand they behave as if they are really concerned about disabled people but on the other hand, they detest disabled people. In front of Tara and Chandan, Roopa shows her as if she dislikes Prema and Nalini but after outside of their house, Roopa joins Prema and Malini and they make fun at Tara's family.

1. Sexuality of Disabled People.

This is another major controversial issue which is related to sexual understanding of disabled people. In the book titled, *The Sexual Politics of Disability* (Shakespeare et al 1996) argues that the sexuality of disabled people is always undermined. They are treated either asexual or a lustful one. This is clear in the present play as well. In the text, Roopa was the first one who starts talking about love, romantic relationship when she was with Chandan. She even asks Chandan whether he had any girlfriend, when Chandan says no, Roopa goes further and asks whether he would like to have one. This makes Chandan to think that Roopa loves him and he tries to touch her. After feeling Chandan's touch, Roopa makes a mess. She flung various abusive words like horrible thing, monster, rapist, liar, creepy thing at Chandan. Roopa's notion about Chandan's sexual ability is clear by the following statement by Roopa;

Roopa. "I'm sorry. I'm just not that type. And personally, I don't think we are-you know-compatible. If you get what I mean."

Roopa even suggests a girl, named Freni Narangiwalla, who is mentally retarded. So, this clearly shows the negative attitude of able-bodied people.

2. Conclusion:

India has a long way to achieve the barrier-free, dignified life of disabled people. Even in the twenty first century, where the world is become virtual still some people's mentality about disabled person is filled with prejudice, biases, superstition. It is the need of the hour to remove these notions. We must re-read the classical texts and as well as literary works to find out the prejudiced treatment of disabled people.

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